

PCS 1900 Interference Simulation for Personal Communications Services Testing, Evaluation, and Modeling

James G. Ferranto¹

National Telecommunications and Information Administration
Institute for Telecommunication Sciences
325 Broadway
Boulder, CO 80303

ABSTRACT

A generic methodology for personal communications services self-interference modeling is applied to the Global System for Mobile-based PCS 1900. The resulting system-specific model is discussed in detail, and is used to produce output noise and interference waveforms suitable for implementation in a real-time hardware channel simulator, or as a component of a link-level software simulation. Different deployment scenarios are then used to generate example PCS 1900 interference waveforms, along with corresponding statistical analyses of interference waveform properties. The model described in this paper is particularly well-suited for support of efficient PCS system evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Complete specification of the personal communications services (PCS) RF channel must include a credible model of the system-specific noise and interference (N/I) environment. Incidental channel impediments are termed "noise," and originate from both natural and artificial sources. "Interferers," by contrast, are waveforms intentionally radiated in the RF channel that disrupt or degrade a desired waveform. Interferers are generated by sources both external and internal to the affected PCS system, and may include other wireless systems sharing a common geographical area and frequency band.

Preliminary studies of the noise environment at 2 GHz show that the natural noise contribution is relatively small [1]. Interferers, by contrast, can be a major hindrance to wireless communication at 2 GHz. This is particularly true in a multiple access environment using microcellular deployment. PCS system capacity is thus interference-limited.

PCS systems are largely untested in actual deployment scenarios. Because predeployment field testing of all aspects of an actual PCS system is prohibitively time-consuming and expensive, other evaluation methods are required. These include real-time hardware simulation of the PCS channel, and software simulation of the PCS network. Hardware simulation of the PCS channel provides an economical, controlled environment for PCS equipment on the link-level. In addition, link- and network-level

software simulation techniques can be used to provide predictions of PCS system performance.

For hardware implementation, a quantitative description of the interference waveform is required. Unfortunately, most descriptions of the interference environment in the literature [2-5] present statistical models of the interference waveform behavior, rather than a model of the waveform itself. However, complex multiple access waveforms from numerous mobile stations may create an interference environment that cannot be described by a single distribution function.

Development of a real-time testing capability involves software simulation of the interference waveform, then adaptation of the results to hardware capable of real-time waveform processing. Ideally, model development and validation should be conducted by an independent PCS system evaluator. Models should be cross-compatible for each of the PCS technologies under test.

To aid assessment of proposed PCS technologies, the Institute for Telecommunication Sciences (ITS) has implemented a PCS network evaluation program that provides performance metrics, interoperability studies, and scenario plans for present and future PCS system operation. To date, ITS has developed system-specific interference models, implementable in hardware, for two licensed PCS technologies: the Global System for Mobile (GSM)-based PCS 1900, and code division multiple access (CDMA) based on IS-95. This paper describes the PCS 1900 model.

II. PCS CELLULAR GEOMETRY AND GENERIC INTERFERENCE EXPRESSIONS

Development of the ITS intrasystem interference waveform based on spatial considerations includes specification of a generic PCS cellular system geometry, i.e., one suited to CDMA or time division multiple access (TDMA). A hexagonal cellular geometry is used, with each cell having six adjacent cells. A single base station is located at the center of each cell. The following assumptions apply to the PCS cellular geometry:

1. All cells within the PCS system are the same size.
2. Each cell contains N_m mobile stations.
3. One RF carrier is simulated per cell.
4. A "primary cell" contains the base station or mobile stations encountering interference.

¹This paper was prepared while Mr. Ferranto was with the Institute for Telecommunication Sciences. He is presently with the Alta Group of Cadence Design Systems, located in Golden, CO.

The primary cell is the focus of the interference waveform simulation. On the uplink, it contains the base station which is experiencing interference from mobile stations outside the primary cell transmitting on the same RF frequency. On the downlink, it includes nearby base station transmissions that interfere with mobile stations in the primary cell.

$\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$ is the complex baseband expression for the interference waveform from the n^{th} interferer in interfering cell k . Depending on the link direction, the interferer may be either a mobile station or a base station. For uplink, n represents the n^{th} interfering mobile station in the k^{th} cell. For TDMA systems, $\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$ is defined over one time slot on the uplink. For other technologies, such as CDMA, $\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$ may not be time-limited. For downlink, n indicates the n^{th} mobile station in the primary cell experiencing interference from the base station in interfering cell k . In the downlink case, $\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$ is defined over one frame for TDMA systems, and is not time-limited for CDMA systems.

$\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$ is the basic building block for the interference waveform expressions. In the N/I model, it is the only expression referenced to the transmitter (i.e., all other expressions represent the interference waveform incident at the receiver). All other interference functions are expressed as summations of $\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$. For example,

$\overline{x_{FI(k,-)}}(t)$ is defined as the sum of all uplink interferer mobile station waveforms created in interfering cell k , incident at the primary cell's base station.

$\overline{x_{FI}}(t)$ is the aggregate uplink interference waveform incident at the primary cell's base station.

$\overline{x_{FI(-,n)}}(t)$ is the downlink interference waveform caused by all interfering base stations, as seen by the n^{th} mobile station in the primary cell.

Expressions for the uplink and downlink interference functions depend on the technology. However, generic expressions can be formed with parameter specification of a CDMA- or TDMA-based technology. These generic expressions are shown below, with the parameter b specifying CDMA or TDMA.

For uplink,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{x_{FI(k,-)}}(t) &= \sum_{n=0}^{N_I - 1} \overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t - nbT_U - \frac{r_{k,n}}{c}) a_{k,n}(r_{k,n}, \theta_{k,n}) \\ \overline{x_{FI}}(t) &= \sum_{k=0}^{N_I - 1} \overline{x_{FI(k,-)}}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and for downlink,

$$\overline{x_{FI(-,n)}}(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{N_I - 1} \overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t - \frac{r_{k,n}}{c}) a_{k,n}(r_{k,n}, \theta_{k,n}), \quad (2)$$

where, for both Equations (1) and (2): c is the speed of waveform propagation, T_U is the duration of a TDMA time slot, N_U is the number of mobile stations per cell, N_I is the number of interfering cells, $r_{k,n}$ is the distance between the point interferer and the receiver, $\theta_{k,n}$ is the angle of the point interferer with respect to the receiver, $a_{k,n}(r_{k,n}, \theta_{k,n})$ is a propagation loss and Doppler function, $r_{k,n}/c$ is the propagation delay, and b indicates TDMA ($b = 1$) or CDMA ($b = 0$).

Figures 1 and 2 show the uplink and downlink relationships, respectively, between a single interferer and receiver. This geometry is used repeatedly to locate all interferers.

Figure 1. Uplink interferer geometry.

Figure 2. Downlink interferer geometry.

III. PCS 1900 GAUSSIAN MINIMUM-SHIFT KEYING MODEL

To obtain a PCS 1900 interference waveform, a model of the physical layer, based on [6], was developed. PCS 1900 employs 200-kHz RF channels in a frequency division duplexing scheme.

The licensed uplink band (1850-1910 MHz) and downlink band (1930-1990 MHz) each theoretically support up to 298 PCS 1900 simplex RF channels (not including two 200-kHz guard bands). Frequency reuse, block frequency allocations, frequency hopping algorithms, and specific equipment designs further restrict the number of concurrent active RF channels in a given cell. PCS 1900 TDMA is based on eight time slots per frame, with 156.25 bit durations allocated per time slot, including guard times. Each time slot lasts 0.5769 ms, and the total modulation rate is approximately 270.8 kb/s. The data rate per user depends on the type of burst used within each time slot, and the number of time slots used per frame per user.

For N/I modeling purposes, the data content of the interferer is not important, as long as sufficient randomness exists in the data stream. Important factors are the modulation scheme, transmitted power levels, propagation environment, and geometric distributions of the interferers. Interference modeling techniques allow abstraction of all communication devices that manipulate the data stream before modulation. This is shown in Figure 3, which is applicable to both uplink and downlink.

Figure 3. Abstracted physical layer configuration for PCS 1900.

The theoretical modulated RF carrier waveform for PCS 1900-based Gaussian minimum-shift keying (GMSK) is converted to complex baseband form for implementation in the interference model. Equation (3) represents the PCS 1900-based GMSK complex envelope from a single transmitter,

$$\bar{x}(t, \alpha) = \sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{T}} \exp[j\phi(t, \alpha) + j\phi_0], \quad (3)$$

where α represents values of a digital information alphabet sequence, $\phi(t, \alpha)$ is the GMSK phase term defined in [6], T is the bit duration, E_s is the energy/modulating bit, and ϕ_0 is a random phase term that is constant over the entire time slot. This expression applies to both base station and mobile station transmitters.

For GMSK, the two possible pulses, corresponding to $\alpha_i \in [-1, 1]$, are generated by exciting a pulse shaping filter with impulse response $g(t)$. Excitations corresponding to the two possible symbol values are represented by $u_{-1}(t) = -\delta(t)$ and $u_{+1}(t) = \delta(t)$, where $\delta(t)$ is the Dirac delta function.

For $u(t) = u_{+1}(t) = \delta(t)$, $\alpha_{+1}g(t) = g(t)$. Similarly, for $u(t) = u_{-1}(t) = -\delta(t)$, $\alpha_{-1}g(t) = -g(t)$. Pulses equal to $\pm g(t)$ are precomputed and transmitted every T seconds, where $g(t)$ represents input symbol $\alpha_i = 1$, and $-g(t)$ represents input symbol $\alpha_i = -1$.

The PCS 1900 GMSK phase is most easily expressed in the time domain. Again, the PCS 1900 GMSK pulse $g(t)$ defined in [6] is the convolution of a Gaussian filter $h(t)$ with the rectangular function, $g(t) = h(t) \otimes \text{rect}(t/T)$. The convolution can be performed in the time domain. The result is given by Equation (4):

$$g(t) = \frac{1}{2T} \left[\text{erfc} \left(\frac{2\pi B(t - \frac{T}{2})}{\sqrt{2 \ln 2}} \right) - \text{erfc} \left(\frac{2\pi B(t + \frac{T}{2})}{\sqrt{2 \ln 2}} \right) \right]. \quad (4)$$

The phase term $\phi(t, \alpha)$ in Equation (3) is calculated by integrating Equation (4). The result is given by Equation (5).

$$\phi(t) = \frac{\pi}{4T} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2 \ln 2}}{2\pi B} \right) \left[\int_{u_1 = \frac{2\pi B}{\sqrt{2 \ln 2}}(-nT - \frac{T}{2})}^{\frac{2\pi B}{\sqrt{2 \ln 2}}(t + \frac{T}{2})} \text{erf}(u_1) du_1 - \int_{u_2 = \frac{2\pi B}{\sqrt{2 \ln 2}}(-nT - \frac{T}{2})}^{\frac{2\pi B}{\sqrt{2 \ln 2}}(t - \frac{T}{2})} \text{erf}(u_2) du_2 \right] \quad (5)$$

Numerical integration was used to compute the phase in Equation (5), since $\text{erf}(x)$ is not analytically integrable. Integration limits ranged from $t = -nT$ to $t = mT_p$, where m is an iteration counter defined from $m = 1$ to $m = N$, N is the number of phase term samples, and T_p is the phase expression's sampling interval. An adaptive-recursive Newton-Cotes algorithm was used for the integration. Section IV applies these equations to simulation.

IV. PCS 1900 INTERFERENCE EXPRESSIONS AND SIMULATION

For characterization of the total intrasystem interference environment for PCS 1900, the description of the single PCS 1900 modulator must be extended to represent the numerous interferers typically encountered at any given time during a call session. This is accomplished by duplicating the single PCS 1900 modulator expression once for each of the interferers, and distributing them via the geometric expressions described in Section III. In addition to geometric distribution, the expressions of Section III also incorporate delay, propagation loss, and Doppler functions which can be chosen arbitrarily. Multipath may be included by duplicating each single interferer N_p times, where N_p is the integer number of paths. Each path must be delayed and weighted as specified by an appropriate multipath model. The uplink intercell interference is presented below (see [7] for the corresponding downlink simulation).

Equation (1) describes generic expressions for uplink intrasystem interference. Because PCS 1900 is a TDMA technology, the parameter b is given the value 1 to simulate the time slot offsets from each mobile station in an interfering cell. The modified Equations (1) and (3) become:

$$\bar{x}_{FI(k,n)}(t, \alpha) = \sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{T}} \exp[j\phi_{FI(k,n)}(t, \alpha) + j\phi_{0, FI(k,n)}] \quad (6)$$

where $\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$ represents the interference waveform created by the n^{th} mobile station in interfering cell k , defined over one time slot. Note that $\overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t)$ now becomes a function of α , n , and k , where

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{x_{FI(k,-)}}(t) &= \sum_{n=0}^{N_U-1} \overline{x_{FI(k,n)}}(t - nT_U - \frac{r_{k,n}}{c}) a_{k,n}(r_{k,n}, \theta_{k,n}) \\ \overline{x_{FI}}(t) &= \sum_{k=0}^{N_I-1} \overline{x_{FI(k,-)}}(t),\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

and $\alpha = \alpha(k, n)$ represents the symbol stream from the n^{th} mobile station in cell k . The continuously modulated phase, $\phi_{FI(k,n)}(t, \alpha)$, is defined over one time slot, and $\phi_{0, FI(k,n)}$ is a random phase term that is constant for the time slot. $\phi_{FI(k,n)}(t, \alpha)$ is given as:

$$\phi_{FI(k,n)}(t, \alpha) = \sum_{l=1}^{N_{\text{bits}}} \alpha_l \phi(t - lT), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T_U. \quad (8)$$

In Equation (8), T is the modulated symbol duration, N_{bits} is the number of bits (symbol durations) per time slot, and T_U is the duration of a time slot. $\phi(t)$ is given by Equation (5), and represents the phase component due to a single positive ($\alpha_l = +1$) modulated GMSK symbol. Because only two symbol states exist for GMSK, $\phi(t)$ and $-\phi(t)$, (corresponding to $\alpha_l = +1$ and $\alpha_l = -1$, respectively), the phase term for the entire time slot may be expressed as time-delayed versions of $\phi(t) = \phi_{FI(k,n)}(t, \alpha_l)_{l=0}$, scaled by either $+1$ or -1 . Note that each symbol spans more than T seconds, therefore symbols will overlap. The phase term was calculated using the integration method described in Section III.

From Equation (7), $\overline{x_{FI(k,-)}}(t)$ represents the sum of all interfering mobiles from the k^{th} interfering cell incident at the primary cell's base station, and $\overline{x_{FI}}(t)$ is the aggregate interference waveform from all N_I interfering cells. Note that $\overline{x_{FI(k,-)}}(t)$ and $\overline{x_{FI}}(t)$ are defined over one PCS 1900 frame (eight time slots), corresponding to 4.6 ms. Simulation parameters were then chosen for the equations. A summary of parameter values is given in Table 1

Simulation of the PCS 1900 uplink interference provided the aggregate interference waveform caused by nearby interfering cells, as seen at the primary cell's base station receiver. Code was written in Matlab™, and executed on a Hewlett-Packard 9000-700 Series™ platform.² A few assumptions were made to simplify the computations, and to randomize certain parameters as follows:

- All interfering cells for a given iteration of the program are equidistant from the primary cell's base station.
- Each simulation iteration calculates the aggregate waveform from an equidistant layer of interfering cells.

²Certain commercial equipment, instruments, systems, or materials are identified in this paper. In no case does such identification imply recommendation or endorsement by the National Telecommunications and Information Administration, nor does it imply that the material or equipment identified is necessarily the best available for the purpose.

For example, the interference waveform from cells adjacent to the primary cell will be computed in one iteration, since all cells are an equal distance from the primary cell. Since two different distances are needed for the second layer of interfering cells, two iterations are required. The total waveform is computed by adding several simulation iterations together. Obtaining the interference waveform due to interferers in both adjacent and second layer cells therefore requires three simulation iterations.

- All interfering cells transmit on the same RF carrier frequency. Cells not contributing to the overall interference waveform, (e.g. resulting from a cell reuse pattern), may be "zeroed out" during the computation.
- PCS 1900 frames from interfering cells are aligned (this may be changed as a simulation parameter).
- Symbols are not aligned from interferer to interferer. A random $U(0, T]$ delay is incorporated in each time slot.

Table 1 Summary of reverse link parameter values.

Parameter/Function	Description	Value
N_{bits}	Number of bits (symbol durations) per time slot.	156.25
N_U	Number of time slots per RF carrier.	8
N_I	Number of interfering cells.	Integer variable
T	Modulated symbol duration.	$6/(1.625 \times 10^6)$ s
T_U	Time slot duration.	$N_{\text{bits}} T$
$\alpha = \alpha(k, n)$	Symbol stream from the n^{th} mobile in cell k .	Random or user-defined
$\phi_{0, FI(k,n)}$	Random phase term that is constant over each interfering mobile station's time slot.	Random or user-defined
$\sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{T}}$	Maximum transmission level from each mobile interferer.	2 V
c	Interference waveform propagation speed.	Typically 3×10^8 m/s
$a_{k,n}(r_{k,n}, \theta_{k,n})$	Propagation loss /Doppler function.	Many models possible
BT	Bandwidth-time product.	0.3

Many different N/I scenarios may be created by setting the simulation parameters accordingly, and consequently a large number of different simulation studies may be conducted. As an example, simulations were run for the default values listed in Table 1. Two simple cases were chosen to demonstrate the capabilities of the simulation tool. In case 1, six interfering cells, all adjacent to the primary cell, are simulated. Case 2 simulates fifty interfering cells that are all equidistant from the primary cell.

For case 2, significant overlap in coverage area occurs, while case 1 reflects a more realistic scenario. Three plots are created for each case, showing statistics of the aggregate interference waveform in the following order: 1) the voltage envelope

Figure 4. Voltage envelope histogram for case 1.

Figure 5. Power envelope histogram for case 1.

Figure 6. Phase histogram for case 1.

Figure 7. Voltage envelope histogram for case 2.

histogram, 2) the power envelope histogram, and 3) the phase distribution histogram.

Results for Case 1. Figures 4, 5, and 6 show the voltage envelope, power envelope, and phase histograms, respectively, of the interference waveform caused by six adjacent interfering cells. The voltage envelope distribution in Figure 4 appears Rayleigh-distributed, although distorted in form. The large value at zero is caused by the guard times, and the simulation assumption that frames in adjacent cells are aligned (when frames are aligned, so are the guard times, resulting in a large number of zero values). Randomization of frame alignment in the simulation simply involves circularly rotating each interfering cell waveform component before aggregation.

Similarly, the power envelope distribution appears as a distorted exponential in Figure 5. The phase distribution of Figure 6 is roughly uniformly distributed on the interval $[-\pi, \pi)$. Again, the

large count value at zero is caused by the guard times.

Results for Case 2. In Figures 7, 8, and 9, the number of simulated interfering cells was increased to fifty, with all other parameters the same as for case 1. Note that the voltage envelope profile given in Figure 7 appears more Rayleigh-distributed, the power envelope in Figure 8 more exponential, and the phase distribution in Figure 9 more uniform than those calculated for case 1.

Non-Gaussian Effects. By setting the power levels explicitly for each interfering mobile station, it is readily demonstrated that the interference waveform is not purely Gaussian. This is demonstrated for an extreme case in Figure 10, which shows the resulting distorted amplitude envelope when a single interfering mobile station in case 1 has its transmitted waveform multiplied by a factor of ten.

Figure 8. Power envelope histogram for case 2.

Figure 9. Phase histogram for case 2.

Figure 10. Voltage envelope for case 1, with the addition of a single dominant interferer.

Outputs from the simulation may be used directly in a real-time hardware channel simulator by repeating an interference waveform of integer frame length. The number of samples per frame is flexible, and implementable in commercially-available waveform generators. The simulated waveform may also be abstracted using statistical methods, at the cost of losing some attributes inherent in the actual waveform.

V. CONCLUSION

N/I models are essential for realistic characterization of the operating environment for proposed PCS technologies. As a justification, examples for PCS 1900 demonstrated that many environmental and systematic influences affect the statistics of the aggregate interference waveform, and that a Gaussian distribution assumption is too simplistic in many cases. Channel simulation using these N/I models provides a valuable PCS evaluation capability, and provides an alternative to expensive PCS field testing.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.D. Spaulding, "The natural and man-made noise environment in personal communication services bands," NTIA Report 94-330.
- [2] R. Prasad, A. Kegel, and A. de Vos, "Performance of microcellular mobile radio in a cochannel interference, natural, and man-made noise environment," *IEEE Trans. Vehic. Tech.*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 33-40, Feb. 1993.
- [3] Y.D. Yao and A.U.H. Sheikh, "Investigations into cochannel interference in microcellular mobile radio systems," *IEEE Trans. Vehic. Tech.*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 114-123, May 1992.
- [4] J. Zou, V.K. Bhargava, and Q. Wang, "Reverse link analysis and performance evaluation for DS-CDMA cellular systems," *IEEE Internat. Symp. on Personal, Indoor, and Mobile Radio Proc.*, BC 1.2, pp. 50-54, 1994.
- [5] R.F. Diesta and J.P. Linnartz, "Using Laplace transforms to compute performance of mobile radio links," *IEEE Internat. Symp. on Personal, Indoor, and Mobile Radio Proc.*, B 3.3, pp. 301-305, 1994.
- [6] "Draft Proposed American National Standard - Air Interface Specification for 1.8- to 2.0-GHz Frequency Hopping Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) for Personal Communication Services," JTC(AIR)/94.10.31-231R5, Oct. 31, 1994.
- [7] J. G. Ferranto "Interference simulation for personal communications services testing, evaluation, and modeling," upcoming NTIA Report.